

Biochemical parameters and glycation products in chronic experimental type 2 diabetes in rats

Plamena Panayotova¹, Gergana Toteva², Boris Dinkov¹

¹ Department Pharmacology and Toxicology, Faculty Pharmacy, Medical University – Pleven, Pleven, Bulgaria

² Vivarium, Medical University – Pleven, Pleven, Bulgaria

³ Medical Center “Berbatov”, Yambol, Bulgaria

⁴ Department of Medical Physics, Biophysics, Pre-clinical and Clinical Sciences, Faculty Pharmacy, Medical University – Pleven, Pleven, Bulgaria

⁵ Department of Anatomy, Histology, Cytology and Biology, Faculty Medicine, Medical University – Pleven, Pleven, Bulgaria

⁶ Department of Pathology, Medical Faculty, Trakia University, Stara Zagora, Bulgaria

⁷ Center of Competence in Personalized Medicine, 3D and Telemedicine, Robotic and Minimally Invasive Surgery “Leonardo da Vinci”, Medical University – Pleven, Pleven, Bulgaria

Corresponding author: Galya Stavreva (galia.stavreva@mu-pleven.bg)

Received 13 October 2025 ♦ Accepted 28 October 2025 ♦ Published 1 December 2025

Citation: Panayotova P, Toteva G, Dinkov B, Tsankova V, Berbatov D, Yordanova-Laleva P, Atanasova M, Gulubova M, Stavreva G (2025) Biochemical parameters and glycation products in chronic experimental type 2 diabetes in rats. *Pharmacia* 72: 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.3897/pharmacia.72.e174742>

Abstract

This study investigated changes in serum levels of protein glycation products, specifically fructosamine, methylglyoxal, and advanced glycation end products (AGEs), in rats with a chronic experimental model of type 2 diabetes induced by a high-fat diet and low-dose streptozotocin. Anthropometric, metabolic, and biochemical parameters were monitored. We observed an early and sustained increase in fructosamine and methylglyoxal, followed by a progressive accumulation of AGEs over the 28-week follow-up period. This experimental model enables the investigation of glycation products not only as biomarkers of disease development, severity, and complications but also as potential therapeutic targets through inhibition of their formation, enhancement of their clearance, or modulation of their receptor actions.

Keywords

Advanced glycation end products, fructosamine, methylglyoxal, type 2 diabetes, Wistar rats

Introduction

The spread of diabetes mellitus (DM) has increased over the past two decades and will be one of the major global health problems in the coming years. DM is associated with a wide spectrum of acute and long-term compli-

cations that substantially contribute to global morbidity and mortality (Forbes and Cooper 2013). Hyperglycemia is a principal pathogenic mechanism associated with the advancement of diabetic complications, resulting in the activation or heightened activity of various metabolic pathways, including the polyol pathway, protein kinase

C, and the synthesis of advanced glycation end products (AGEs) (Park et al. 2019; Mengstie et al. 2022). AGEs are diverse substances generated via non-enzymatic interactions between reducing sugars and proteins, lipids, or nucleic acids, a process referred to as glycation (Perrone et al. 2020). AGEs may be exogenous or generated endogenously within the body (Vadakedath and Kandi 2018). Endogenous AGEs are predominantly produced through the Maillard reaction, wherein aldehyde groups of reducing sugars like glucose (Glu), fructose, and ribose engage in a sequence of non-enzymatic reactions with terminal amino groups of proteins, nucleic acids, and phospholipids, resulting in the creation of reactive carbonyl intermediates (Fishman et al. 2018). Glycation is a spontaneous and gradual process under physiological settings, as it lacks enzymatic catalysis and generally necessitates many days to weeks (Rabbani and Ahn 2019). In contrast, AGEs are formed more rapidly and accumulate extensively in the circulation and various tissues under conditions of chronic hyperglycemia (Ahmad et al. 2014; Vadakedath and Kandi 2018). One of the mechanisms underlying diabetes-related complications associated with inflammation (e.g., atherosclerosis) is AGE-induced alteration of the extracellular matrix (ECM) (Garay-Sevilla et al. 2021). The accumulation of AGEs in the ECM is also linked to other diabetes complications, such as micro- and macroangiopathies, increased risk of retinopathy, and chronic kidney disease (Koska et al. 2018).

Long-lived structural proteins such as collagen and elastin are particularly prone to glycation (Guo and Xu 2017). AGE accumulation is accelerated under hyperglycemic conditions due to increased availability of monosaccharide substrates (Khalid et al. 2022). Once formed, AGEs are chemically stable and contribute to tissue damage until the modified proteins are degraded (Guo and Xu 2017). AGEs exert their pathogenic effects primarily through binding to the receptor for AGEs (RAGE), activating downstream signaling pathways including NF κ B, MAPKs, and JNK. These pathways modulate the expression of pro-inflammatory cytokines, chemokines, growth factors, adhesion molecules, and extracellular matrix proteins (Kuzan 2021). Glycation and oxidative stress are interdependent processes—collectively referred to as glyco-oxidation. AGEs both promote the generation of reactive oxygen species (ROS) and disrupt endogenous antioxidant systems. Overall, AGEs contribute to the development of diabetic complications through receptor-mediated signaling cascades and structural alterations of the extracellular matrix via cross-link formation (Singh et al. 2014). Therefore, glycation products in tissues or the bloodstream may be considered promising biomarkers and predictors of diabetic complications (Simó-Servat et al. 2018).

A variety of experimental models of diabetes have been widely used to study the underlying mechanisms of metabolic dysregulation, the development of diabetic complications, and the evaluation of novel drugs and therapeutic interventions. No animal model meets all these

aspects, but they provide more or less information that is close to the course of diabetes in humans. Experimental diabetes is generally induced by chemical, surgical, and genetic manipulations (Madhariya et al. 2023; Algül and Ozcelik 2025). Agents such as streptozotocin (STZ), alloxan, ferric nitrilotriacetate, dithizone, and anti-insulin serum are frequently employed for this purpose. Other models are induced by viruses, diet or food with or without obesity, surgical procedures, or the deletion or over-expression of a specific gene (Kottaisamy et al. 2021). In vitro models using beta-cell lines and pancreatic islets, human stem cells and organoid cultures, as well as enzymatic in vitro tests, e.g., by inhibition of α -glucosidase activity, are increasingly relevant (Janapati and Junapudi 2024). Research on AGEs, including glycated collagen, has predominantly focused on experimental models of type 1 diabetes (T1D), most often induced through the administration of STZ or alloxan (Meng et al. 1996; Turk et al. 1999; Degenhardt et al. 2002; Candido et al. 2003; Bhatti et al. 2011; Li et al. 2023). While these models have provided important insights into the mechanisms of AGE formation, they do not fully capture the pathophysiological features of type 2 diabetes (T2D).

Considering the much higher global prevalence of T2D, it is critical to investigate AGE accumulation and its relationship with metabolic dysfunction in models that more accurately reflect this condition. To address this gap, we employed a modified chronic experimental model of T2D in rats, in which a high-fat diet (HFD) is combined with a low dose of STZ. This approach replicates two key hallmarks of T2D: the development of insulin resistance and the progressive decline in insulin secretion from pancreatic islet β -cells (Skovsø 2014; Brito et al. 2025). By using this model, we aimed to better characterize the production of AGEs and metabolic disturbances associated with T2D.

Materials and methods

Ethical approval

The study was carried out in accordance with national legislation and institutional policies and complied with international standards for the care and use of experimental animals (European Directive 2010/63/EU). The experimental protocol was reviewed and approved by the Bulgarian Food Safety Agency (Protocol No. 444/06.10.2025).

Animals and housing

A total of 48 male Wistar rats (10–12 weeks of age; initial body weight 180–220 g) were used. The rats were provided by the Experimental and Breeding Base for Experimental Animals—Slivnitsa. Animals were housed under controlled environmental conditions (temperature 20–24 °C, relative humidity 55% \pm 10%, 12 h light/12 h dark cycle) with ad libitum access to standard food and water. Following a 4-week adaptation period, the animals were randomly allocated into

two groups: control (C, n = 24) and diabetic (D, n = 24). At 4, 12, and 28 weeks after diabetes induction, eight animals from each group were sacrificed for sample collection.

Diet and experimental protocol

The control group was maintained on a standard laboratory rodent diet (Combined Rodents Feed, Melhran Ltd.) throughout the study (Fig. 1). The diet consisted of wheat, corn, sunflower meal, soybean meal (containing GMO code number MON-04032-6, approved for EU import), wheat bran, and a premix of supplemental nutrients (calcium carbonate, monocalcium phosphate, sodium chloride, lysine, VMP, methionine, prefect, sodium bicarbonate, optiphos, alkozel, and calcium carbonate). The D group was fed a high-fat diet (HFD) providing 43% of total energy intake, prepared by supplementing the standard chow with lard (Andonova et al. 2023). After 4 weeks on HFD, animals were fasted overnight and subsequently received a single intraperitoneal (i.p.) injection of streptozotocin (STZ; mixed anomers, S0130, Sigma-Aldrich/Merck) at a dose of 35 mg/kg body weight, freshly dissolved in 0.1 M citrate buffer (pH 4.5). On day 7 post-injection, animals with fasting blood Glu levels > 12 mmol/L were considered diabetic. Control animals received an equivalent volume of citrate buffer (vehicle) and remained on the standard diet.

Body weight was recorded weekly, while food and water intake were measured daily.

Figure 1. Design of the experiment.

Sample collection

At 4, 12, and 28 weeks post-induction of diabetes, eight rats per group were anesthetized, and blood samples were collected by puncture of the heart. Samples were centrifuged at 3000 rpm for 15 min at 4 °C, and serum was stored at –20 °C until further analysis.

Biochemical assays

The following metabolic parameters were assessed using an automated biochemical analyzer (Roche Hitachi C-311):

- Blood Glu: enzymatic hexokinase UV test
- Total cholesterol (TChol), triglycerides (TG), low-density lipoprotein cholesterol (LDL-C), and high-density lipoprotein cholesterol (HDL-C)
- Very-low-density lipoprotein cholesterol (VLDL-C), calculated using Friedewald's formula: VLDL-C = TG/5
- Fructosamine (FA): colorimetric method.

Immunological assays

Serum levels of selected immunological markers were quantified using commercially available ELISA kits, according to the manufacturers' instructions. All samples were analyzed in duplicate.

- Insulin (Ins): Elabscience (cat. no. E-EL-R3034); results expressed as pg/mL
- Methylglyoxal (MGO): MyBiosource (cat. no. MBS2505842); results expressed as ng/mL
- Advanced glycation end products (AGEs): Cloud-Clone Corp. (cat. no. CEB353Ge); results expressed as ng/mL.

Assessment of insulin resistance, using the homeostasis model assessment of insulin resistance (HOMA-IR), beta-cell function (HOMA-β), and triglyceride-Glu (TyG) index:

- HOMA-IR is determined based on the results obtained from the measurement of insulin and fasting blood sugar using the formula:

$$\text{HOMA-IR} = \text{Ln} \frac{\text{Fasting Insulin}(\mu\text{U/mL}) \times \text{Fasting Glu}(\text{mmol/L})}{22.5}$$

- HOMA-β index is determined using the formula:

$$\text{HOMA-}\beta = \frac{20 \times \text{Fasting Insulin}(\mu\text{U/mL})}{\text{Fasting Glu}(\frac{\text{mmol}}{\text{L}}) - 3.5}$$

- TyG index is determined using the formula:

$$\text{TyG} = \text{Ln} \frac{\text{Triglycerides}(\text{mg/dL}) \times \text{Fasting Glu}(\text{mg/dL})}{2}$$

Histological examinations

The formalin-fixed tissue pieces were embedded in paraffin blocks. Sections 5 μm thick were stained with hematoxylin/eosin. Light microscopy was used for histological evaluation.

Statistical analysis

Statistical analysis was performed using Statgraphics Centurion 18 and Microsoft Excel 2010. Data are presented as mean ± standard error of the mean (mean ± SEM). One-way ANOVA followed by the Bonferroni post hoc test was

used to analyze differences between groups, and Student's t-test was applied for pairwise comparisons. A p-value < 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results

Body weight, food, and water intake

Throughout the 8-month experimental period (7 months following diabetes induction), the body weight (BW) of the animals was monitored weekly. At baseline, rats in the C and D groups had comparable initial BW (206.45 ± 4.16 g and 204.6 ± 4.6 g, respectively). After 4 weeks on HFD, all animals exhibited a statistically significant increase in BW relative to baseline (Fig. 2). No statistically significant differences were observed between the groups, although the increase in BW was more pronounced in the experimental group. In the diabetic group, 1 week after STZ administration, BW showed a slight reduction to 295.5 ± 6.4 g, despite a higher food intake in this group (34.00 ± 0.78 g versus 30.92 ± 1.59 g in the control group), with no statistically significant difference. From the third week following diabetes induction, both the control and diabetic groups displayed a progressive increase in BW that continued until the end of the study. By week 28, animals in the C group had a higher BW compared to the D group, although this difference did not reach statistical significance. During the last 3 months of the experiment, the average daily food intake was significantly lower in the C group (37.55 ± 0.99 g) compared to the D group (52.36 ± 3.49 g; $p < 0.05$).

Water consumption was as follows: 45.48 ± 1.67 mL as the initial value for both groups and 44.25 ± 2.89 mL and 51.19 ± 1.76 mL for the C group at week 12 and at the end of the experiment, respectively. The corresponding values for the experimental group were 48.12 ± 2.32 mL and 72.60 ± 4.93 mL, with a statistically significant difference both compared to the C group ($p < 0.05$) and in the dynamics of the indicator within the D group ($p < 0.001$).

Figure 2. Body weight dynamics of diabetic (n = 8) and control (n = 8) groups. Values are presented as mean \pm SEM. Statistically significant differences between groups: * $p \leq 0.05$; ** $p \leq 0.001$. Abbreviations: W = week, 0W = after diet, before STZ injection.

Carbohydrate metabolism

The data presented in Figs 3, 4 demonstrate that serum fasting Ins and blood Glu concentrations in the C group remained close to baseline values, showing no statistically significant differences throughout the experimental period. In the D group, following a 4-week HFD regimen, fasting blood sugar levels increased from 5.92 ± 1.2 to 6.83 ± 1.05 mmol/L, although the change did not reach statistical significance (Fig. 2). Persistent significant hyperglycemia was observed in this group during the entire study, with the lowest blood Glu level recorded at week 28 (22.57 ± 2.43 mmol/L).

Figure 3. Dynamics of blood Glu in diabetic (n = 8) and control (n = 8) groups. Values are presented as mean \pm SEM. Statistically significant differences between groups: * $p \leq 0.001$; ** $p \leq 0.0001$. Abbreviations: W = week, 0W = after diet, before STZ injection.

A lower serum Ins concentration was recorded in the D group at week 4 after STZ injection, which persisted throughout the study period. The differences compared to the C group were statistically significant at weeks 4 and 12 (Fig. 4). The serum Ins level in the experimental group remained reduced throughout the study period, with statistically significant differences compared to the C group observed at weeks 4 and 12.

Figure 4. Dynamics of serum insulin level in diabetic (n = 8) and control (n = 8) groups. Values are presented as mean \pm SEM. Statistically significant differences between groups: * $p < 0.05$; ** $p \leq 0.001$. Abbreviation: W = week after STZ injection.

The HOMA-IR index, a known marker of insulin resistance, showed an upward trend over the course of the experiment, with its value slightly increased in the D group compared to the C group at the end of week 4; a statistically significant difference was found in this parameter at weeks 12 and 28 (Fig. 5). Within the D group, HOMA-IR was significantly higher at the last two time points compared to the initial value ($p < 0.001$). The values of the HOMA- β index were significantly lower in the D group compared to the C group at all examined time points, indicating impaired beta-cell function (Fig. 6).

Figure 5. HOMA-IR of diabetic and control groups. Values are presented as mean \pm SEM. Statistically significant differences between groups: ** $p \leq 0.001$. Abbreviation: W = week after STZ injection.

Figure 6. HOMA- β index of diabetic and control groups. Values are presented as mean \pm SEM. Statistically significant differences between groups: ** $p \leq 0.001$; *** $p < 0.0001$. Abbreviation: W = week after STZ injection.

The TyG index is a relatively recent surrogate marker for assessing insulin resistance and metabolic risk, which shows significantly higher values in the experimental group, recorded at week 4 (after STZ administration) and persisting until the end of the experiment (Fig. 7).

Figure 7. TyG index of diabetic and control groups. Values are presented as mean \pm SEM. Statistically significant differences between groups: * $p \leq 0.005$. Abbreviation: W = week after STZ injection.

Lipid metabolism

The changes in the lipid profile of the C and D groups are presented in Table 1. In rats with experimentally induced diabetes and maintained on HFD throughout the entire experimental period, a statistically significant increase in TChol levels was observed compared to the control animals at all examined time points. LDL concentrations remained unchanged over the course of the experiment and did not differ significantly between the D and C groups. In contrast, the levels of VLDL and TG were significantly elevated at week 12 compared to the controls ($p < 0.001$), as well as compared to their levels at week 4 ($p < 0.05$). At week 28, their values in the D group remained significantly higher than in the controls ($p < 0.05$), and a statistically significant difference was observed in HDL levels between the C and D groups.

Glycation products

Post hoc multiple comparison tests revealed a significant increase in serum fructosamine levels (FA) in the D groups compared to the C groups (Fig. 8), whereas

Table 1. Serum concentration of lipids in the control (n = 8) and diabetic (n = 8) groups.

Time	Group	TChol	LDL	HDL	VLDL	Trig
W 4	C	1.53 \pm 0.096	0.33 \pm 0.027	0.93 \pm 0.07	0.27 \pm 0.03	1.06 \pm 0.13
	D	2.00 \pm 0.19 *	0.33 \pm 0.03	0.93 \pm 0.07	0.74 \pm 0.16	2.29 \pm 0.78
W 12	C	1.34 \pm 0.06	0.32 \pm 0.08	0.83 \pm 0.07	0.15 \pm 0.01	0.73 \pm 0.07
	D	2.77 \pm 0.28 *	0.39 \pm 0.17	1.04 \pm 0.12	1.34 \pm 0.27 **	5.36 \pm 1.36 **
W 28	C	1.32 \pm 0.05	0.39 \pm 0.027	0.81 \pm 0.10	0.19 \pm 0.07	0.63 \pm 0.08
	D	2.09 \pm 0.17 *	0.38 \pm 0.03	1.12 \pm 0.06 **	0.69 \pm 0.16 *	3.62 \pm 0.86 *

Notes: Values are presented as mean \pm SEM. Statistically significant differences between groups: * $p < 0.05$; ** $p \leq 0.001$. Abbreviation: W = week after STZ injection.

FA levels in control rats remained stable throughout all time points examined. Although, throughout the entire study period after diabetes induction, the levels of MGO in the D animals were moderately increased (~10% at week 4; ~20% at week 12; ~30% at week 28), no statistically significant differences were observed compared to the C groups (Fig. 9).

Figure 8. Dynamics of serum fructosamine level in diabetic ($n = 8$) and control ($n = 8$) groups. Values are presented as mean \pm SEM. Statistically significant differences between groups: * $p < 0.05$. Abbreviation: W = week after STZ injection.

Figure 9. Dynamics of serum methylglyoxal (MGO) level in diabetic ($n = 8$) and control ($n = 8$) groups. Values are presented as mean \pm SEM. Abbreviation: W = week after STZ injection.

Both groups of rats showed similar AGEs values at week 4 after STZ injection. The level of AGEs increased with increasing duration of hyperglycemia and reached 14.4 ± 1.74 ng/mL at week 28, with a statistically significant difference compared to controls (Fig. 10).

Histological examination

The pancreas from control rats showed normal islets of Langerhans. By the 12th week after STZ injection, the diabetic pancreata exhibited marked destruction of most large islet β -cells. The remaining islets appeared reduced in size, with the presence of inflammatory cell infiltration and dilated intralobular and interlobular ducts (Fig. 11).

Figure 10. Dynamics of serum advanced glycation end products (AGEs) level in diabetic ($n = 8$) and control ($n = 8$) groups. Statistically significant differences between groups: * $p < 0.05$. Abbreviation: W = week after STZ injection.

Figure 11. Pancreas histology in diabetic (A) and control (B) rats. Hematoxylin and eosin (H&E) staining, $\times 50$ (A); $\times 200$ (B).

Discussion

In recent decades, interest in the glycation process has increased, as it represents a key physiological mechanism associated with aging and has been increasingly implicated in the development of various pathological conditions and diseases, including diabetes, cancer, cardiovascular and neurodegenerative disorders, as well as SARS-CoV-2 infections and the manifestations of long COVID (Bronowicka-Szydełko et al. 2024). Serious pathogenic consequences of glycation include inflammation, oxidative stress, carbonyl stress, cytotoxicity, genotoxicity, and changes in protein structure and function. Glycation adducts may therefore serve not only as valuable diagnostic and prognostic biomarkers but also as potential therapeutic targets in various disorders.

Our study is focused on a chronic experimental model of T2D and the investigation of glycation products. For this purpose, we reviewed 29 studies in which diabetes was induced in Wistar rats using HFD for at least 3 weeks combined with a low dose of STZ, ranging from 25 to 45 mg/kg b.w. According to the literature, this model reproduces to a large extent the clinical features and underlying mechanisms of T2D in humans. It provides relatively rapid changes in metabolic, histological, inflammatory, and oxidative markers, as well as in metabolic signaling pathways in tissues targeted by T2D (Skovso 2014; Brito et al. 2025). In the studies we analyzed, the duration of

animal follow-up after confirmation of diabetes varied substantially, with extended observation periods reported at day 56 (Cai et al. 2019; Omid et al. 2019; Mangali et al. 2020; Xu et al. 2020; Ghasemi et al. 2023; Khoramipour et al. 2023; A-Elgadir et al. 2024; Bagheripour et al. 2024; Mahmoud et al. 2024), day 80 (Ghiasi et al. 2019), day 90 (Sohrabipour et al. 2018), and up to a maximum of 140 days (Rezazadeh et al. 2021). No studies were identified that investigated alterations in glycation products.

We applied a model with a 4-week diet in which more than 40% of total caloric intake was derived from fats, achieved by supplementing the diet with lard. According to Andonova et al. (2023), this diet leads to impaired Glu metabolism by the end of the 4th week and to an increase in HOMA-IR. The experimental group remained on HFD until the end of the experiment, i.e., week 28 after the induction of diabetes with STZ (35 mg/kg). The cytotoxic agent we used, STZ [2-deoxy-2-(3-(methyl-3-nitrosoureido)-D-glucopyranose)], is a nitrosourea analog derived from *Streptomyces achromogenes*. It enters cells and nuclei via the GLUT-2 transporter, causing alkylation and fragmentation of DNA, which leads to necrosis of pancreatic β -cells, the production of nitric oxide, and reactive oxygen species (Eleazu et al. 2013).

During the first days following STZ administration, a reduction in BW (Fig. 2), food, and water intake was observed, which is likely due to the acute toxic effect of STZ (Goyal et al. 2016). Analysis of BW showed a statistically significant increase in both the D and C groups at week 28 compared to baseline. Statistically significantly lower weights were found in group D during the first 3 months. At the end of the experiment, there was no statistically significant difference between the two groups. Our data are consistent with those reported by other authors who have studied chronic experimental diabetes over 12 weeks (Sohrabipour et al. 2018; Zafar and Naqvi 2010). The measured visceral adipose tissue showed higher values in the experimental group only at the initial points of intervention, but by week 28, it was significantly lower (data not shown).

Throughout the experimental period, we monitored the dynamics of blood Glu levels to determine whether hyperglycemia persisted until the end of the experiment. The sustained elevation of fasting Glu in the D group, exceeding 22 mmol/L even at week 28, confirms the stability of the hyperglycemic state induced by the combination of HFD and STZ administration (Fig. 4). In contrast, Glu levels in the C group remained within the normal physiological range. The persistently low serum Ins concentrations observed throughout the study period support the presence of impaired β -cell function (Fig. 5). At 28 weeks, an increased serum insulin concentration was observed, but at levels lower than control, which proves that by the end of the follow-up period, the impaired endocrine pancreatic secretion was not restored. The gradual increase in HOMA-IR values over time indicates the progressive development of insulin resistance in Wistar rats, consistent with previous reports (Antunes et al. 2016; Chao et al. 2018). The marked suppression of the HOMA- β index

suggests reduced secretory capacity of pancreatic β -cells in the D group. Nevertheless, the serum Ins levels, as well as the histological findings, imply that the secretory function was not completely abolished. This observation aligns with other studies reporting partial β -cell preservation when diabetes is induced by an HFD combined with a low dose of STZ (Omid et al. 2019; Andonova et al. 2023; Bagheripour et al. 2023; A-Elgadir et al. 2024). In addition to HOMA-IR, we applied the fasting triglyceride-Glu (TyG) index to further evaluate insulin resistance. The TyG index has recently gained recognition as a practical surrogate marker for impaired insulin sensitivity in obesity, prediabetes, and type 2 diabetes (Mohd Nor et al. 2016). Its significant elevation in the D group compared to the C group throughout the experiment supports its utility in detecting insulin resistance in experimental models. Moreover, the parallel changes observed in HOMA-IR and TyG suggest that both indices reliably reflect the metabolic disturbances characteristic of T2D.

Decreased Ins secretion and Ins sensitivity are relevant not only for impaired Glu metabolism but also for lipid dysregulation (Saltiel and Kahn 2001; Elkanawati et al. 2024). Al-Mrabeh (2020) formulated the “twin cycle” hypothesis in T2D. According to it, higher food intake in insulin resistance leads to elevated TG levels and hepatic steatosis. This disrupts insulin-controlled glycogen synthesis, stimulates gluconeogenesis, and consequently increases blood Glu levels. Concurrently, elevated circulating TGs promote lipotoxicity in the islets of Langerhans, impairing insulin secretion and further increasing hyperglycemia and beta-cell dysfunction. Experimental studies using HFD models support this mechanism, demonstrating that HFD induces inflammation and interferes with insulin signaling, mainly through ceramides and diacylglycerol (DAG). Ceramides further contribute to insulin resistance by inhibiting Akt/PKB, while DAG activates protein kinase C and disrupts insulin signaling (Elkanawati et al. 2024). In our study, biochemical analyses of lipid profiles revealed increased mean values of TChol, VLDL, and most notably TG. LDL level did not exhibit significant changes during the study period, nor did it increase in the D group compared to the C group. In contrast to several studies that reported increased LDL levels, we did not observe such a trend. HDL levels were higher than LDL in both groups. Interestingly, the D group showed higher mean HDL levels, with a statistically significant difference at week 28. Many authors reported findings similar to our results regarding TChol and TG. However, other studies have not observed such changes in TChol and TG (Omid et al. 2019; Xiang et al. 2019). The increase in HDL levels observed in our study is consistent with Gheibi (2017), while other studies have reported no significant change in HDL concentrations (Omid et al. 2019; Lv et al. 2020).

It should be emphasized that lipid profiles differ substantially between humans and rats. The predominant lipoprotein in plasma and the carrier of cholesterol in humans is LDL, whereas in rats, HDL predominates.

Rats exhibit a characteristic lipoprotein profile with low LDL levels and high HDL levels (Olivero-David et al. 2011; Santos-López et al. 2018). Rats are categorized as HDL-animals (Bocanegra et al. 2009), showing very efficient uptake of VLDL by LDL receptors and less transfer of apolipoprotein B from VLDL to LDL and TG.

In addition to choosing a reliable and reproducible animal model of T2D that could provide a long follow-up period, our other main task was to monitor the changes in the serum level of fructosamine (FA, early glycation products), methylglyoxal (MGO, intermediate product), and AGEs at 4, 12, and 28 weeks after diabetes induction. Serum FA levels in the experimental group were statistically higher than in the C group at 4 weeks, with the most significant variation occurring at 12 weeks after diabetes induction and persisting throughout the study period. MGO levels were higher in diabetic animals during the follow-up period, but without a significant difference compared to controls. The AGE levels studied at 4 weeks were comparable to those in controls, increased at 12 weeks, and were significantly higher at 28 weeks compared to controls ($p < 0.05$). FA was discovered more than 35 years ago as a marker for blood Glu control, reflecting the average glycaemic level over the previous 2–3 weeks (Armbruster 1987; Nagasaka et al. 1988). FA (1-amino-1-deoxyfructose) is a stable ketoamine formed by linking the aldehyde group of a carbohydrate to the N-terminal amino acid of proteins. It binds primarily to circulating albumin but can also bind to globulins and lipoproteins. The reversible intermediate Schiff base product is formed. The Schiff base product can be converted back to Glu and protein or undergo an Amadori rearrangement to form stable fructosamine. Since albumin is the most abundant of the serum proteins, FA is primarily a measure of glycated albumin. FA is an early step in the process of non-enzymatic glycation of proteins. If glycated proteins remain in circulation, they can undergo further reactions and become AGEs. FA has limited but real predictive value for diabetic complications, especially when HbA1c is unreliable or when short-term control is being assessed (Goldstein et al. 2004). FA and glycated albumin are strongly associated with diabetic retinopathy, as well as the risk of developing chronic kidney disease (Selvin et al. 2013).

MGO is a key product of dicarbonyl stress and plays a key role in diabetes-related microangiopathies such as diabetic retinopathy, nephropathy, and neuropathy, as well as in endothelial dysfunction, cardiac remodeling, and disruption of insulin signaling (Schalkwijk and Stehouwer 2020). MGO is a small, highly reactive α -dicarbonyl compound formed mainly under chronic hyperglycemia due to accelerated glycolytic flux (Rabbani and Ahn 2019). In an experimental study, healthy mice injected with a Glu solution after fasting exhibited a rapid rise in plasma MGO levels (Zang et al. 2023). MGO is metabolized via the glyoxalase system (Glo-1 and II with glutathione), which converts MGO into D-lactate. In diabetes, this pathway is often overloaded or insufficient. Brouwers et al. (2011) reported that elevated Glu and MGO levels were significantly re-

duced in Glo-1 transgenic rats with STZ-induced diabetes. Similarly, in patients with T2D and acute coronary events, higher MGO levels have been associated with reduced erythrocyte Glo-1 activity (Bora et al. 2023). Studies using cell cultures and animal models have demonstrated that increased MGO concentrations induce metabolic dysregulation and may even trigger new-onset diabetes (Chaudhuri et al. 2018; Xue et al. 2024; Gugliucci 2025).

MGO promotes post-translational modification of peptides and proteins, leading to the formation of AGEs, primarily the arginine-derived methylglyoxal-hydroimidazolone 1 (MG-H1) and carboxyethyl-lysine, among others (Thornalley 2010). MGO also covalently modifies DNA, and more recently, stable covalent MGO adducts have been identified on RNA (Gonzalez 2015). These RNA modifications decrease mRNA stability and impair translation. Notably, RNA MGO adducts (e.g., CEG) show a stronger correlation with type 2 diabetes and its complications than DNA MGO adducts (e.g., CEdG). Once formed, AGEs interact with their membrane receptor RAGE, a member of the immunoglobulin receptor superfamily (Kalapos 1992; Dobrucki et al. 2023). Beyond its crucial role in innate immunity, RAGE activation triggers numerous intracellular signaling cascades, including the upregulation of IL-1 β , VCAM-1, and TNF- α , and the phosphorylation of JNK and p38 MAPK (Erusalimsky 2021). Another important pathway involves the activation of NADPH oxidase, resulting in redox imbalance and the generation and accumulation of reactive oxygen species (Korac et al. 2019; Seryogina et al. 2024). Consequently, AGEs affect key cellular processes such as chemotaxis, angiogenesis, oxidative stress, proliferation, and apoptosis (Khalid et al. 2022). In addition, AGE-RAGE interactions impair insulin signaling by inhibiting GLUT4 translocation, thereby contributing to insulin resistance (Song et al. 2021). Proteins of the extracellular matrix are also subject to glycation, which alters their physical and mechanical properties, as well as their interactions with integrins and other matrix components (Bonnans 2014). Furthermore, AGEs within ECM proteins form cross-links, thereby exacerbating vascular stiffness (Schalkwijk and Stehouwer 2020). Proteins with a slow turnover rate, such as fibrillar collagens, are highly vulnerable to glycation. Due to the long half-life of these proteins, the glycation process progresses slowly and is largely irreversible. Overall, glycation products are not only indicators of impaired carbohydrate metabolism but also pathogenic factors in the development of diabetes and its complications.

Conclusion

In conclusion, our model of T2D, induced by HFD over a 28-week experimental period with a single STZ injection at a dose of 35 mg/kg b.w., represents a reliable and reproducible model of chronic T2D. Fructosamine, as an early glycation product, and methylglyoxal, as an intermediate product, were elevated at week 4 after diabetes induction

and remained high until the end of the experiment. Advanced glycation end products increased after week 12 and continued to rise throughout the study period. This experimental model enables the investigation of glycation products not only as biomarkers of disease development, severity, and complications but also as potential therapeutic targets through inhibition of their formation, enhancement of their clearance, or modulation of their receptor actions.

Acknowledgements

The support with the material and technical base of project BG16RFPR002-1.014-0002-C001 “Center of Competence in Personalized Medicine, 3D and Telemedicine, Robotic and Minimally Invasive Surgery,” funded by PRIDST 2021–2027, co-financed by the EU, is highly appreciated.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors’ representatives participating in the study.

Experiments on animals: Bulgarian Food Safety Agency (Protocol No. 444/06.10.2025).

References

- A-Elgadir TM, Shati AA, Alqahtani SA, Ebrahim HA, Almohaimeed HM, ShamsEldeeen AM, Haidara MA, Kamar SS, Dawood AF, El-Bidawy MH (2024) Mesenchymal stem cells improve cardiac function in diabetic rats by reducing cardiac injury biomarkers and downregulating JAK/STAT/iNOS and iNOS/Apoptosis signaling pathways. *Molecular and Cellular Endocrinology* 591: 112280. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mce.2024.112280>
- Ahmad S, Khan MS, Akhter F, Khan MS, Khan A, Ashraf JM, Shahab U (2014) Glycoxidation of biological macromolecules: a critical approach to halt the menace of glycation. *Glycobiology* 24(11): 979–990. <https://doi.org/10.1093/glycob/cwu057>
- Algül S, Ozcelik O (2025) Comprehensive review of animal models in diabetes research using chemical agents. *Laboratory Animals* 59(3): 356–363. <https://doi.org/10.1177/00236772241296199>
- Al-Mrabeh A (2020) Pathogenesis and remission of type 2 diabetes: what has the twin cycle hypothesis taught us? *Cardiovascular Endocrinology & Metabolism* 9(4): 132–142. <https://doi.org/10.1097/XCE.0000000000000201>
- Antunes LC, Elkfury JL, Jornada MN, Foletto KC, Bertoluci MC (2016) Validation of HOMA-IR in a model of insulin-resistance induced by a high-fat diet in Wistar rats. *Archives of Endocrinology and Metabolism* 60: 138–42. <https://doi.org/10.1590/2359-3997000000169>
- Armbruster DA (1987) Fructosamine: structure, analysis, and clinical usefulness. *Clinical Chemistry* [1987 Dec 1] 33(12): 2153–2163. <https://doi.org/10.1093/clinchem/33.12.2153>
- Bagheripour F, Jeddi S, Kashfi K, Ghasemi A (2024) Anti-obesity and anti-diabetic effects of L-citrulline are sex-dependent. *Life Sciences* [Feb 15] 339: 122432. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lfs.2024.122432>
- Bhatti R, Sharma S, Singh J, Ishar MP (2011) Ameliorative effect of Aegle marmelos leaf extract on early stage alloxan-induced diabetic cardiomyopathy in rats. *Pharmaceutical Biology* 49(11): 1137–1143. <https://doi.org/10.3109/13880209.2011.572077>
- Bocanegra A, Bastida S, Benedí J, Nus M, Sánchez-Montero JM, Sánchez-Muniz FJ (2009) Effect of seaweed and cholesterol-enriched diets on postprandial lipoproteinaemia in rats. *British journal of nutrition* [2009 Dec] 102(12): 1728–39. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S000711450999105X>
- Bonnans C, Chou J, Werb Z (2014) Remodelling the extracellular matrix in development and disease. *Nature Reviews Molecular Cell Biology* 15(12): 786–801. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nrm3904>

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Use of AI

No use of AI was reported.

Funding

This study was funded by University Research Project No. 21/2024, Medical University – Pleven.

Author contributions

P.P. conducted experiments, collected and analysed the data, and interpreted the results, writing the manuscript; G.T. conducted experiments, collected the data; B.D. conducted experiments; V.T. conducted experiments; D.B. participated in the interpretation of the results; M.A. conducted and analysed immunological studies, edited and reviewed the manuscript; P.L. conducted biochemical studies; M.G. conducting histological studies; G.S. developed the study concept and methodology, prepared the methodological approach, wrote and edited the manuscript, and coordinated teamwork. All authors reviewed and approved the final version of the manuscript.

Author ORCIDs

Boris Dinkov <https://orcid.org/0009-0004-1625-7414>

Pavlina Yordanova-Laleva <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6227-7342>

Milena Atanasova <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2814-1932>

Maya Gulubova <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0615-6412>

Galya Stavreva <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4026-1980>

Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

- Bora S, Adole PS, Vinod KV, Pillai AA, Ahmed S (2023) The genetic polymorphisms and activity of glyoxalase 1 as a risk factor for acute coronary syndrome in South Indians with type 2 diabetes mellitus. *Gene* 885: 147701. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gene.2023.147701>
- Brito AK, Mendes AV, Timah Acha B, Santos Oliveira AS, Lopes Macedo J, Suzuki Cruzio A, Prianti MD, Abreu RR, Lucarini M, Durazzo A, do Carmo de Carvalho e Martins M (2025) Experimental models of type 2 diabetes mellitus induced by combining hyperlipidemic diet (HFD) and streptozotocin administration in rats: an integrative review. *Biomedicines* 13(5): 1158. <https://doi.org/10.3390/biomedicines13051158>
- Bronowicka-Szydełko A, Gostomska-Pampuch K, Kuzan A, Pietkiewicz J, Krzystek-Korpaczka M, Gamian A (2024) Effect of advanced glycation end-products in a wide range of medical problems including COVID-19. *Advances in Medical Sciences* 69(1): 36–50. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.advms.2024.01.003>
- Cai H, Chen S, Liu J, He Y (2019) An attempt to reverse cardiac lipotoxicity by aerobic interval training in a high-fat diet-and streptozotocin-induced type 2 diabetes rat model. *Diabetology & Metabolic Syndrome* 11(1): 43. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13098-019-0436-8>
- Chao PC, Li Y, Chang CH, Shieh JP, Cheng JT, Cheng KC (2018) Investigation of insulin resistance in the popularly used four rat models of type-2 diabetes. *Biomedicine & Pharmacotherapy* 101: 155–61. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biopha.2018.02.084>
- Chaudhuri J, Bains Y, Guha S, Kahn A, Hall D, Bose N, Gugliucci A, Kapahi P (2018) The role of advanced glycation end products in aging and metabolic diseases: bridging association and causality. *Cell Metabolism* 28(3): 337–352. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cmet.2018.08.014>
- Dion F, Dumayne C, Henley N, Beauchemin S, Arias EB, Leblond FA, Lesage S, Lefrançois S, Cartee GD, Pichette V (2017) Mechanism of insulin resistance in a rat model of kidney disease and the risk of developing type 2 diabetes. *PLOS ONE* 12(5): e0176650. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0176650>
- Dobrucki IT, Miskalis A, Nelappana M, Applegate C, Wozniak M, Czerwinski A, Kalinowski L, Dobrucki LW (2024) Receptor for advanced glycation end products: biological significance and imaging applications. *Wiley Interdisciplinary Reviews: Nanomedicine and Nanobiotechnology* 16(1): e1935. <https://doi.org/10.1002/wnan.1935>
- Eleazu CO, Eleazu KC, Chukwuma S, Essien UN (2013) Review of the mechanism of cell death resulting from streptozotocin challenge in experimental animals, its practical use and potential risk to humans. *Journal of Diabetes & Metabolic Disorders* 12(1): 60. <https://doi.org/10.1186/2251-6581-12-60>
- Elkanawati RY, Sumiwi SA, Levita J (2024) Impact of lipids on insulin resistance: insights from human and animal studies. *Drug Design, Development and Therapy* 18: 3337–3360. <https://doi.org/10.2147/DDDT.S468147>
- Erusalimsky JD (2021) The use of the soluble receptor for advanced glycation-end products (sRAGE) as a potential biomarker of disease risk and adverse outcomes. *Redox Biology* [2021 Jun 1] 42: 101958. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.redox.2021.101958>
- Fishman SL, Sonmez H, Basman C, Singh V, Poretsky L (2018) The role of advanced glycation end-products in the development of coronary artery disease in patients with and without diabetes mellitus: a review. *Molecular Medicine* 24(1): 59. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s10020-018-0060-3>
- Forbes JM, Cooper ME (2013) Mechanisms of diabetic complications. *Physiological Reviews* 93(1): 137–188. <https://doi.org/10.1152/physrev.00045.2011>
- Friedewald WT, Levy RI, Fredrickson DS (1972) Estimation of the concentration of low-density lipoprotein cholesterol in plasma, without use of the preparative ultracentrifuge. *Clinical Chemistry* 18(6): 499–502. <https://doi.org/10.1093/clinchem/18.6.499>
- Garay-Sevilla ME, Rojas A, Portero-Otín M, Uribarri J (2021) Dietary AGEs as exogenous boosters of inflammation. *Nutrients* 13(8): 2802. <https://doi.org/10.3390/nu13082802>
- Ghasemi A, Gheibi S, Kashfi K, Jeddi S (2023) Anti-oxidant effect of nitrite in the pancreatic islets of type 2 diabetic male rats. *Iranian Journal of Basic Medical Sciences* 26(4): 420.
- Gheibi S, Kashfi K, Ghasemi A (2017) A practical guide for induction of type-2 diabetes in rat: Incorporating a high-fat diet and streptozotocin. *Biomedicine & Pharmacotherapy* 95: 605–13. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biopha.2017.08.098>
- Ghiasi R, Naderi R, Sheervalilou R, Alipour MR (2019) Swimming training by affecting the pancreatic Sirtuin1 (SIRT1) and oxidative stress, improves insulin sensitivity in diabetic male rats. *Hormone Molecular Biology and Clinical Investigation* 40(3): 20190011. <https://doi.org/10.1515/hmbci-2019-0011>
- Goldstein DE, Little RR, Lorenz RA, Malone JI, Nathan D, Peterson CM, Sacks DB (2004) Tests of glycemia in diabetes. *Diabetes Care* 27(7): 1761–173. <https://doi.org/10.2337/diacare.26.2007.S106>
- Goyal SN, Reddy NM, Patil KR, Nakhate KT, Ojha S, Patil CR, Agrawal YO (2016) Challenges and issues with streptozotocin-induced diabetes—a clinically relevant animal model to understand the diabetes pathogenesis and evaluate therapeutics. *Chemico-Biological Interactions* 244: 49–63. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cbi.2015.11.032>
- Gugliucci A (2025) Exploring glyoxalase strategies for Gugliucci managing sugar-induced chronic diseases. *Life* 15(5): 794. <https://doi.org/10.3390/life15050794>
- Guo H, Xu Y (2017) Role of advanced glycation end products in the progression of diabetes mellitus. *Global Journal of Obesity, Diabetes and Metabolic Syndrome* 4(1): 024–035. <https://doi.org/10.17352/2455-8583.000019>
- Janapati YK, Junapudi S (2024) Progress in experimental models to investigate the in vivo and in vitro antidiabetic activity of drugs. *Animal Models and Experimental Medicine* 7(3): 297–309. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ame2.12442>
- Kalapos MP (1992) Medical aspects of methylglyoxal metabolism. *Orvosi Hetilap* 133(10): 587–591. [PMCID: PMC12112988]
- Khalid M, Petroianu G, Adem A (2022) Advanced glycation end products and diabetes mellitus: mechanisms and perspectives. *Biomolecules* 12(4): 542. <https://doi.org/10.3390/biom12040542>
- Khoramipour K, Rezaei MH, Madadzadeh E, Hosseini MS, Soltani Z, Schierbauer J, Moser O (2023) High intensity interval training can ameliorate hypothalamic appetite regulation in male rats with type 2 diabetes: the role of Leptin. *Cellular and molecular neurobiology* 43(8): 4295–307. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10571-023-01421-w>
- Korac B, Kalezić A, Pekovic-Vaughan V, Korac A, Jankovic A (2021) Redox changes in obesity, metabolic syndrome, and diabetes. *Redox biology* 42: 101887. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.redox.2021.101887>
- Koska J, Saremi A, Howell S, Bahn G, De Courten B, Ginsberg H, Beisswenger PJ, Reaven PD (2018) Advanced glycation end products, oxidation products, and incident cardiovascular events in patients

- with type 2 diabetes. *Diabetes Care* 41(3): 570–576. <https://doi.org/10.2337/dc17-1740>
- Kottaisamy CP, Raj DS, Prasanth Kumar V, Sankaran U (2021) Experimental animal models for diabetes and its related complications – a review. *Laboratory Animal Research* 37(1): 23. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s42826-021-00101-4>
- Kuzan A (2021) Toxicity of advanced glycation end products (Review). *Biomedical Reports* 14(5): 46. <https://doi.org/10.3892/br.2021.1422>
- Lv Q, Le L, Xiang J, Jiang B, Chen S, Xiao P (2020) Liver transcriptomic reveals novel pathways of empagliflozin associated with type 2 diabetic rats. *Frontiers in Endocrinology* 11: 111. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fendo.2020.00111>
- Madhariya R, Dixena B, Ram A, Vyasa A, Jain AK (2023) Experimental animal models: tools to investigate antidiabetic activity. *Current Pharmaceutical Design* 29(2): 79–94. <https://doi.org/10.2174/1381612829666221220115649>
- Mahmoud LM, Mageed AA, Saadallah JM, Youssef MF, Rashed LA, Ammar HI (2024) Interleukin 1 β receptor blocker (Anakinra) and regenerative stem cell therapy: two novel approaches effectively ameliorating diabetic cardiomyopathy. *Naunyn-Schmiedeberg's Archives of Pharmacology* 397(10): 8023–41. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00210-024-03152-1>
- Mangali S, Bhat A, Jadhav K, Kalra J, Sriram D, Venuganti VV, Dhar A (2020) Upregulation of PKR pathway mediates glucolipotoxicity induced diabetic cardiomyopathy in vivo in Wistar rats and in vitro in cultured cardiomyocytes. *Biochemical Pharmacology* 177: 113948. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bcp.2020.113948>
- Mengstie MA, Chekol Abebe E, Behaile Teklemariam A, Tilahun Mulu A, Agidew MM, Teshome Azezew M, Zewde EA, Agegnehu Teshome A (2022) Endogenous advanced glycation end products in the pathogenesis of chronic diabetic complications. *Frontiers in Molecular Biosciences* 9: 1002710. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmolb.2022.1002710>
- Mohd Nor NS, Lee S, Bacha F, Fayli H, Arslanian S (2016) Triglyceride glucose index as a surrogate measure of insulin sensitivity in obese adolescents with normoglycemia, prediabetes, and type 2 diabetes mellitus: comparison with the hyperinsulinemic-euglycemic clamp. *Pediatric Diabetes* 17(6): 458–65. <https://doi.org/10.1111/vedi.12303>
- Nagasaka Y, Fujii S, Yaga K, Matsumura S, Kaneko T (1988) Clinical application of measuring serum fructosamine as an index of glycaemic control in diabetic patients. *The Bulletin of the Yamaguchi Medical School* 35(3–4): 59–62.
- Olivero-David R, Schultz-Moreira A, Vázquez-Velasco M, González-Torres L, Bastida S, Benedit J, Sanchez-Reus MI, González-Muñoz MJ, Sánchez-Muniz FJ (2011) Effects of Nori- and Wakame-enriched meats with or without supplementary cholesterol on arylesterase activity, lipaemia and lipoproteinaemia in growing Wistar rats. *British Journal of Nutrition*. 106(10): 1476–86. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S000711451100198X>
- Omid H, Khorram S, Mesgari M, Asghari-Jafarabadi M, Tarighat-Esfanjani A (2019) The effects of natural nano-sized clinoptilolite and *Nigella sativa* supplementation on blood glucose and lipid profile in rats with type 2 diabetes mellitus. *Progress in Nutrition* 21: 147–53
- Park S, Kang HJ, Jeon JH, Kim MJ, Lee IK (2019) Recent advances in the pathogenesis of microvascular complications in diabetes. *Archives of Pharmacological Research* 42(3): 252–262. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12272-019-01130-3>
- Perrone A, Giovino A, Benny J, Martinelli F (2020) Advanced glycation end products (AGEs): Biochemistry, signaling, analytical methods, and epigenetic effects. *Oxidative Medicine and Cellular Longevity* 2020(6): 3818196–3818213. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2020/3818196>
- Rabbani G, Ahn SN (2019) Structure, enzymatic activities, glycation and therapeutic potential of human serum albumin: a natural cargo. *International Journal of Biological Macromolecules* 123: 979–990. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijbiomac.2018.11.053>
- Rezazadeh H, Sharifi MR, Sharifi M, Soltani N (2021) Gamma-aminobutyric acid attenuates insulin resistance in type 2 diabetic patients and reduces the risk of insulin resistance in their offspring. *Biomedicine & Pharmacotherapy* 138: 111440. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biopha.2021.111440>
- Saltiel AR, Kahn CR (2001) Insulin signalling and the regulation of glucose and lipid metabolism. *Nature* 414(6865): 799–806. <https://doi.org/10.1038/414799a>
- Santos-López JA, Garcimartín A, Bastida S, Bautista-Ávila M, González-Muñoz MJ, Benedit J, Sánchez-Muniz FJ (2018) Lipoprotein profile in aged rats fed chia oil- or hydroxytyrosol-enriched pork in high cholesterol/high saturated fat diets. *Nutrients* 10(12): 1830. <https://doi.org/10.3390/nu10121830>
- Schalkwijk CG, Stehouwer CD (2020) Methylglyoxal, a highly reactive dicarbonyl compound, in diabetes, its vascular complications, and other age-related diseases. *Physiological Reviews* [2020 Jan 1] 100(1): 407–461. <https://doi.org/10.1152/physrev.00001.2019>
- Selvin E, Rawlings AM, Grams M, Klein R, Sharrett AR, Steffes M, Coresh J (2014) Fructosamine and glycated albumin for risk stratification and prediction of incident diabetes and microvascular complications: a prospective cohort analysis of the Atherosclerosis Risk in Communities (ARIC) study. *The Lancet Diabetes & Endocrinology* 2(4): 279–88. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2213-8587\(13\)70199-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2213-8587(13)70199-2)
- Seryogina ES, Kamynina AV, Korojev DO, Volpina OM, Vinokurov AY, Abramov AY (2024) RAGE induces physiological activation of NADPH oxidase in neurons and astrocytes and neuroprotection. *The FEBS Journal* 291(9): 1944–1957. <https://doi.org/10.1111/febs.17086>
- Simó-Servat O, Planas A, Ciudin A, Simó R, Hernández C (2018) Assessment of advanced glycation end-products as a biomarker of diabetic outcomes. *Endocrinology, Diabetes & Nutrition* 65(9): 540–545. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.endinu.2018.06.003>
- Skovso S (2014) Modeling type 2 diabetes in rats using high fat diet and streptozotocin. *Journal of Diabetes Investigation* 5(4): 349–358. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jdi.12235>
- Sohrabipour S, Sharifi MR, Talebi A, Sharifi M, Soltani N (2018) GABA dramatically improves glucose tolerance in streptozotocin-induced diabetic rats fed with high-fat diet. *European Journal of Pharmacology* 826: 75–84. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejphar.2018.01.047>
- Song Q, Liu J, Dong L, Wang X, Zhang X (2021) Novel advances in inhibiting advanced glycation end product formation using natural compounds. *Biomedicine & Pharmacotherapy* 140: 111750. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biopha.2021.111750>
- Thornalley PJ, Waris S, Fleming T, Santarius T, Larkin SJ, Winklhofer-Roob BM, Stratton MR, Rabbani N (2010) Imidazopurinones are markers of physiological genomic damage linked to DNA instability and glyoxalase 1-associated tumour multidrug resistance. *Nucleic acids research* 38(16): 5432–5442. <https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkq306>

- Vadakedath S, Kandi V (2018) Role of Advanced Glycation End products (AGE) in health and disease: An overview. *Biochemistry & Physiology: Open Access* 7: 246. <https://doi.org/10.4172/2168-9652.1000246>
- Xiang J, Lv Q, Yi F, Song Y, Le L, Jiang B, Xu L, Xiao P (2019) Dietary supplementation of vine tea ameliorates glucose and lipid metabolic disorder via akt signaling pathway in diabetic rats. *Molecules* 24(10): 1866. <https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules24101866>
- Xu LN, Yin LH, Jin Y, Qi Y, Han X, Xu YW, Liu KX, Zhao YY, Peng JY (2020) Effect and possible mechanisms of dioscin on ameliorating metabolic glycolipid metabolic disorder in type-2-diabetes. *Phytomedicine* 67: 153139. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.phymed.2019.153139>
- Xue M, Irshad Z, Rabbani N, Thornalley PJ (2024) Increased cellular protein modification by methylglyoxal activates endoplasmic reticulum-based sensors of the unfolded protein response. *Redox Biology* 69: 103025. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.redox.2024.103025>
- Yamagishi H, Komabayashia T (2003) Alteration of glucose metabolism and increased fructosamine in iron-deficiency anemic rats. *Nutrition Research* 23(11): 1547–1553. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0271-5317\(03\)00159-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0271-5317(03)00159-3)
- Zafar M, Naqvi SN (2010) Effects of STZ-induced diabetes on the relative weights of kidney, liver and pancreas in albino rats: a comparative study. *International Journal of Morphology* 28(1): 135–142. <https://doi.org/10.4067/S0717-95022010000100019>
- Zhan J, Chen C, Wang DW, Li H (2022) Hyperglycemic memory in diabetic cardiomyopathy. *Frontiers of Medicine* 16(1): 25–38. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11684-021-0881-2>
- Zhang X, Scheijen JL, Stehouwer CD, Wouters K, Schalkwijk CG (2023) Increased methylglyoxal formation in plasma and tissues during a glucose tolerance test is derived from exogenous glucose. *Clinical Science* 137(8): 697–706. <https://doi.org/10.1042/CS20220753>